

NPM trivial reuse survey

We are a group of researchers from Concordia University (<http://das.encs.concordia.ca>) performing a study on the impact of trivial reuse of Node packages. We are conducting a quick (15 minute) preliminary survey to better understand what developers consider to be a trivial package.

Below, you see a list of packages (clicking on the link will show the source code of the packages), and we would like you to check the box for packages that you think are "trivial". A trivial package is loosely defined in our context and can be thought of as a package that can be quickly and easily coded by yourself, i.e., you do not absolutely need to use this package. If you have any questions, feel free to contact us at eshihab@cse.concordia.ca

* Required

1. How would you best describe yourself? *

Mark only one oval.

- Undergraduate Student
- Graduate Student
- Professional Developer
- Other: _____

2. How much development experience do you have? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- 2-3 years
- 3-5 years
- More than 5 years

3. Which of these packages/source code would you consider to be 'trivial'? CHECK THE BOX FOR THE 'TRIVIAL' PACKAGES ONLY * *

Check all that apply.

- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nathanhoad/s3-signed-request/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/strugee/stratic-extract-header/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/sindresorhus/is-absolute-url/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/vanjacovic/run-wintersmith/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/medokin/node-stupid-gso/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/alpacaaa/rethinkdbdash-timestampable/master/src/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/bunnybones1/urlparam/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/danwkennedy/koa-meta-success/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/SocketCluster/sc-channel/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ganioc/html-stitch/master/tasks/stitch.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/Flet/prettier-bytes/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mbakaitis/bootcheck/master/bootcheck.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/sindresorhus/callsites/master/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/olalonde/maybedone/master/src/index.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/iamdustan/smoothscroll/master/src/smoothscroll.js>
- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/juliangruber/isarray/master/index.js>

4. In the previous question, which attributes did you use to determine that a package was trivial? *

Check all that apply.

- Size
- Complexity
- Code comments
- Other: _____